

Predictors Of Financial Decisions And Financial Performance Based Resource Based View Theory

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Abstract

RBVT explains that companies that use their own special resources can achieve the competition. The product market is very attractive equipment (assets) and they can easily be financially, as well as assets to gain competitive advantage. Innovation is of paramount importance affecting corporate and advertising processes, especially in association systems and industrialization programs. Innovation helps the team to help groups to improve their products more effectively, and customers increase in return. Permanent winnings are a special means of enhancing financial work so that it can gain a competitive advantage. Traditional traditions, innovations, and companies offering plans need funding to improve your financial work.

Introduction

SMI in Bali Province has an important role in Bali's economy, because the data shows that more than 90% of Bali's industry is SMI. The development of SMI in Bali cannot be separated from Bali, which is an archipelago and international tourist destination. Most of the SMI product commodities are to support Bali as a tourist destination. Data on the number of SMI in Bali can be seen from the number of business units as many as 12,048 business units (2014), increasing to 15,134 business units (2019) with an average increase of 6.40 percent every year. The number of workers absorbed as many as 92,997 people (2014) increased to 104,000 (2019) with an average increase of 2.96 percent each year. The investment value of SMI also increased, namely Rp3,419,879,403 million (in 2014) to Rp5,212,096,782 million (in 2019) with an average increase of 17, 47 percent of each year. (Disperindag Province of Bali, 2020). The number of SMI in Bali Province, approximately 81 percent is the Handicraft Industry, which is the leading industry in Bali Province. The export development of Bali Province reached \$ 503,826,213 (in 2014), increasing to \$ 574,276,900 (in 2019) with an average increase of 6.99 percent annually. Based on the export of Bali Province, an average of 60 percent is export of commodities from handicrafts produced by SMI (Disperindag Province of Bali, 2020). 99 percent every year. Based on the export of Bali Province, an average of 60 percent is export of commodities from handicrafts produced by SMI (Disperindag Province of Bali, 2020). 99 percent every year. Based on the export of Bali Province, an average of 60 percent is export of commodities from handicrafts produced by SMI (Disperindag Province of Bali, 2020).

The development of a business can be seen from its performance improvement. Performance for SMI is very important, because this performance determines the continuity of its operations. Company performance is a measure of achievement that can be achieved by the company at a certain time. Abdullah (2013) states that performance is the result of organizational work, which is carried out by employees in accordance with instructions, leadership directions, competence and the ability of employees to develop their reasoning at work. One of the measures of performance is financial performance. Companies that are able to manage their assets effectively and efficiently tend to produce good financial performance, which is realized with a level of profitability. profitability is the company's ability to generate profits during a certain period related to the use of productive assets or capital (funds), as a whole, both debt (foreign capital) and own capital (Horne and Wachowicz, 2017: 87). On the other hand, improving the financial performance of SMI cannot be separated from various hindering problems.

SMI's contribution is very large to the economy in Bali, but SMI itself experiences obstacles in improving its performance. The obstacle faced by SMIs is limited capital (Disperindag Province of Bali, 2012), this is also confirmed by Bashir et al., (2013), Omondi and Muturi (2013) and Matar and Eneizan (2018). Capital is one of the most important resources needed to start and develop Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) (Gilbert et al 2006). Capital is one of the problems faced by SMI, where most SMI have small capital so

that it is difficult to develop. A number of financial institutions are reluctant to provide capital assistance, so most SMIs use private funds to finance business development (Udin, 2014; Kazimoto, 2014). Reluctance of the bank to provide funding assistance, based on the risk of paying back from a very high number of SMIs (Alaudin and Chowdhury, 4 2015). The provision of capital assistance to SMI has not been effective, because the amount of funds is small but the units are many.

Capital problems in SMI are related to company funding decisions. Daud et al., (2016) revealed that funding decisions are important decisions made by companies. Financial managers need to optimize the best financing method using debt or equity to maximize company performance. A funding decision is a decision which involves the form and composition of funding to be used by a company.

RBV (Resource Base View) discusses the company's internal resources and capabilities and their relationship with strategic decision making. In addition, RBV describes how firm resources affect externally competitive outcomes and processes. Additional to the RBV are factors of firm competition and the role of internal resources in the company in determining competitive results. RBV is a theory rooted in the economy, besides, it is content-oriented and strategy formulation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Resource Based View theory views the company as a collection of resources and capabilities (Penrose 1959; Wernerfelt, 1984). The RBV assumption is that the company competes based on resources and capabilities. Differences in company resources and capabilities with competing firms will provide competitive advantages (Peteraf, 1993). Company resources can be divided into three types, namely, tangible, intangible and human resources (Grant, 2002). Ability to show what the company can do with its resources (Amit and Schoemaker, 1993). A higher level of company capability is known as 'capability dynamics' capability dynamics (Teece et al., 1997). Capability dynamics is the company's ability to create, maintain, or change the capabilities of other companies (Winter 1987).

METHOD

This research is classified as qualitative research. Qualitative research is influenced by the philosophy of constructivism, where constructivism has a different view. The understanding or meaning of a phenomenon is formed by the participants and the subjective views of the participants. When participants give their understanding or answer, they speak according to the meaning experienced during social interaction with other people and what they talk about also comes from their personal background. Research findings are formed from a "bottom up" pattern, that is, from an individual perspective to become a broader pattern that ultimately forms a theory. This study tries to analyze the subjective view of the views of several studies on the funding system. Funding system with Pecking Order Theory from 7 Myers and Majluf (1984). Packing order theory emphasizes the internal funding system, with various efforts. This study explores what innovations have been carried out to increase internal funding for SMIs with various studies that have been carried out using the same theory.

RESULTS

According to Resource Based View, the strategy is carried out by allocating resources to market needs when the competitor's capabilities are insufficient so that it will provide effective results for the company. Company resources and capabilities are essential in business-level strategy. And valuable resources that can influence the various efforts that the company does are important in corporate-level strategy (Montgomery and Hariharan, 1991).

At the business level, researchers have examined the relationship between resources and the sustainability of competitive advantage (eg, Dierick and Cool, 1989; Barney, 1991; and Peteraf, 1993). The focus of RBV is on what makes resources superior and why competitors cannot easily find, create or imitate better resources. The answer is the characteristics of resources and capabilities which are referred to as 'strategic assets' (Amit and Schoemaker, 1993). Strategic assets such as a corporate culture which is socially complex, silent and induces habits have become a concern.

At the corporate level, it also pays attention to how strategic assets affect company performance (Montgomery and Wernerfelt, 1988). The influence is not only based on the characteristics of the resource, but also on the communication and coordination mechanisms of the company. These factors allow the company to develop strategic assets down to its business activities. The performance of a company depends on internal consistency among the three elements of the 'corporate triangle strategy' - resources, effort, and organizational mechanisms, which include organizational structure, systems and processes. (Collins and Montgomery, 1998).

The successful growth and sustainability of the company will depend on the development of new resources as well as exploiting old resources (Wernerfelt, 1984). Thus, RBV also pays attention to organizational learning, knowledge accumulation, development capabilities, and the association change process

(Helfat, 2000). The dynamics of RBV pay attention to the relationship of these things (Helfat and Peteraf, 2003).

Innovations made by companies in the role of funding decisions are very important to improve the company's financial performance. The innovations in this research include Marketing Innovation, Product Innovation and Process Innovation which triggers companies to make bigger funding decisions in improving their performance. A company that is always innovating which includes Marketing Innovation, Product Innovation and Process Innovation requires sufficient funding to improve its financial performance. Limited own capital owned by the company, the use of debt is an alternative.

Research on the effect of funding decisions on financial performance has been widely studied such as Shahwan (2018) on Construction and Real Estate Companies in Nigeria; Ahmad et al (2018) at a Consumer Goods company in Malaysia; Hajering et al (2018) on Banking Companies in Indonesia, Muiruri and Wepukhulu (2018); Bag and Dani (2018); at a company listed on The Nairobi Securities Exchange Kenya; Hashim and Hassan (2017) on a construction company in Malaysia. Furthermore, research on SMI conducted by Puspingsih et al., (2015) found that the positive influence of funding decisions on financial performance at SMI in Bali. The same thing was also found by Wiagustini et al., (2019) in the Small Handicraft Industry in Gianyar Regency, Bali.

On the other hand, research findings on the effect of funding decisions on financial performance are found to be different, namely funding decisions have a negative effect on corporate financial performance, as found by Pratheepkanth (2011) on companies listed on the Colombo Stock Exchange Sri Lanka; Ulzana (2015) on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. Furthermore, Bag and Dani (2018) found that funding decisions have no effect on the company's financial performance.

The difference in research findings of the effect of funding decisions on financial performance is the motivation for research to find solutions, so that this research gap research is carried out by adding innovations in this study as predecessor variables. SMI in Indonesia, apart from facing obstacles in capital, also faces challenges, especially in innovating so that it has not been able to perform well. A number of research results explain that innovation can have a significant impact on organizational performance (Bustinza et al., 2019). Innovation is one of the requirements for an organization to survive and become better because it is adaptive to environmental changes so that the output produced can be accepted by customers (Denning, 2005).

Wang and Noe (2010) found that innovation is a company mechanism to produce new products, processes and systems in order to adapt to competition in an ever-changing market. Innovation has become a major topic in organizations, it's just that it is relatively difficult to realize so that organizations experience obstacles and difficulties in competing (Pratoom and Savatsomboon, 2012). At present, innovation has become a necessity for organizations to improve their competitive position so as to improve performance. Innovation has also been shown to be able to help organizations be more resilient (Wang and Noe, 2010; Ikeda and Marshall, 2016) because they tend to be more creative and dynamic in creating new knowledge and skills to produce new products and processes (Parthasarathy et al., 2011).

Innovations which include product innovation, process innovation and marketing innovation require funding in their implementation, this innovation funding affects operational cash flow that comes from internal sources, namely company profitability, but when innovation is higher, the company will seek external funding by using debt to fund it. This funding system is in accordance with the Pecking Order Theory of 7 Myers and Majluf (1984), which reveals that the company initially uses internal funding that comes from profitability for corporate funding, then external funding from debt will be an alternative with more financing, required.

Higher innovation requires greater funding decisions that come from greater debt (Chen et al., 2015). Funding through debt is important in innovation (Choi et al., 2016 and Chibani et al, 2019). Funding for corporate innovation does not always use debt when profitability increases, but external funding that comes from debt will become important as more and more financing is needed. with increasing innovation efforts (Bartoloni, 2013).

Product Innovation

Nataya and Sutanto (2018) conducted a study of Product Innovation on Plastic Manufacturers in Surabaya, which found that Product Innovation had a significant effect on marketing performance. Creative innovation activities through product innovation will increase the company's ability to create quality products which are then expected to increase the company's competitive advantage which in turn has an impact on company performance (Back et al., 2014), and Babkin et al., (2015). Innovation the higher it is found to improve company performance (Abatari, et al., 2016).

Parkman et al., (2012) found that product innovation has a positive effect on marketing performance. Pardi et al., 2014; Tung, 2012; Killa, 2014; that innovation has a significant positive effect on marketing performance. The higher the marketing performance will lead to the overall company performance. Gunday et

al., (2011) exploring the effect of innovation on organization in manufacturing companies in Turkey found a positive effect of product innovation on firm financial performance.

Product innovation is the introduction and development of new types of goods or services that are different from the previous ones and complement the shortcomings of previous discoveries by emphasizing more on the quality aspect as expressed by Atalay et al., (2013). Product innovation is the development of new products, making changes to current product designs or using new techniques and methods in current production methods (Marxt et al., (2004). Product innovation funding affects operating cash flow taken from the company's profitability, when innovation the higher the product, the company will seek external funding by using debt to finance it, this is in accordance with the Pecking Order Theory.

Research on the effect of capital structure as corporate funding decisions on innovation found that innovation has an impact on increasingly large debt financing (Chen at al., 2015). Funding through debt plays an important role in innovation (Choi et al, 2016). Chibani et al., (2019) found that debt has an important role in the financing policies of family companies that carry out innovations in France. Corporate innovation funding is less indebted when operating profitability increases, but the use of external financing from debt increases with increasing innovation efforts (Bartoni, 2013).

Process Innovation

Mr. et al., (2016) revealed that process innovation is a more important factor that affects company performance than product innovation and marketing, especially in organizational structures and manufacturing processes. Habidin and Khaidir (2015) revealed that process innovation helps organizations to increase organizational productivity and quality. Where the quality of the output is improved, the customer will be satisfied and will use it again and thus increase productivity. Subsequently costs will be reduced and eventually get a chance to achieve a competitive advantage. It Has Proven To Be Effective In The Health Care Industry Especially In Malaysia.

Khalid and Kumar (2013) examined the ability of process innovation on organizational performance, a case study of aloud international a company whose operations are in the field of maintenance and power generation with a water transmission system, headquartered in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, found that innovation process capabilities were has a positive impact on organizational performance.

Ar and Baki (2011) conducted a study on managers of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) located in the Turkish science and technology park. The research results show that process innovation has a strong and positive relationship with company performance. Research Gunday et al., (2011) exploring the effect of innovation on organization in manufacturing companies in Turkey found a positive effect of process innovation on firm performance.

Process innovation is the implementation of new or significantly improved production methods, shipping methods, or administrative processes. Process innovation can be viewed as the application of new or improved production or delivery methods that include changes in techniques, equipment and software (Omachonu and Einspruch, 2010). At the beginning of the innovation process, it will affect the operational cash flow taken from the company's profitability, when product innovation is higher, the company will seek external funding by using debt to fund it, this is in accordance with the Pecking Order Theory.

Innovation has an impact on increasing debt financing (Chen et al., 2015). Funding through debt plays an important role in innovation (Choi et al., 2016). Chibani et al., (2019) found that debt has an important role in the financing policies of family companies that carry out innovations in French countries. Corporate innovation funding is less indebted when operating profitability increases, but the use of external financing from debt increases with increasing innovation efforts (Bartoni, 2013).

Marketing Innovation

The linkage of innovation to organizational performance is strengthened by the results of previous research conducted by Noruzy et al. (2013) where it was found that organizational innovation has a direct relationship to company performance. Improving performance through innovation can be done through improving services to consumers. Kafetzopoulos and Psomas (2015) state that innovation ability directly contributes to product quality and operational performance because innovation makes organizations more creative. Organizational creativity contributes to the creation of ideas so as to create innovative products in the market (Carvalho & Roberto, 2012).

Biégas, (2018) examined the effect of marketing innovation capacity on the performance of the clothing industry in Brasilia, it was found that the capacity of marketing innovation is a positive predictor of financial performance and marketing performance. Gunday et al., (2011) exploring the effect of innovation on organization in manufacturing companies in Turkey found a positive effect of marketing innovation on the financial performance of companies. Hogan and Coote, (2014) reveal the effective application of marketing innovation, meaning that the capacity of marketing innovation is related to consumer attractiveness and retention and the achievement of economic results, market performance and financial performance, respectively.

Marketing innovation can help drive the performance of the Small and Medium Enterprises market in Turkey (Aksoy, 2017).

A marketing innovation is a new or significant change in non-functional characteristics such as product design or packaging, place, promotion, and price. For example, changing the design of a related product to change its appearance, not its function or user. Marketing innovation is aimed at better handling customer needs, opening new markets, or positioning the company's products in the market, with the aim of increasing sales (Chandrakhanthan and Karthika, 2007). Marketing innovation funding affects operating cash flow which is taken from the company's profitability, when product innovation is higher, the company will seek external funding by using debt to finance it, this is in accordance with the Pecking Order Theory. Higher innovations to produce product quantity and quality have an impact on greater debt financing (Chen et al., 2015). Funding through debt plays an important role in innovation (Choi et al., 2016). Chibani et al., (2019) found that debt has an important role in the financing policies of family companies that carry out innovations in French countries. Marketing innovation has an impact on improving the capital structure which is the company's funding decision (Wintoro, 2008).

Table 1
Research Mapping Results

Research(Year)	InnovationProduct	InnovationProcess	MarketingInnovation	FundingDecisions	Financial performance
1. Natayaand Sutanto (2018)	x				x
2. Back et al., (2014) and Babkin et al. (2015)	x				x
3. Abatar,et al.,(2016)	x				x
4. Gundayet al.,(2011)	x				x
5. Parkmanet al., (2012)	x				x
6. Chastonand Scoot (2012)	x				x
7. Habidin and Khaidir, (2015).		x			x
8. Khalidand Kumar (2013)		x			x
9. Litaet al.,(2017)		x			x
10.Ar and Tray (2011)		x			x
11. Gunday et al., (2011)		x			x
12. Ungerman et al., (2018).			x		x
13. Rosenbusch et al. (2011)			x		x
14. Gunday et al., (2011)			x		x
15. Hogan and Coote, (2014).			x		x
16. Cascio, (2011),			x		x
17.Biégas (2018)			x		x
18. Aksoy, (2017).			x		x
29. Anik Puspiningsih et al., (2015)				x	x

20. Hashim and Hassan (2017)				x	x
21. Shahwan (2018)				x	x
22. Ahmad et al., (2018)				x	x
23. Hajering et al., (2018)				x	x
24. Muiruri and Wepukhulu (2018);				x	x
25. Bag and Dani (2018);				x	x
26. Wiagustini et al., (2019)				x	x

Source: Researcher, 2020

CONCLUSION

RBVT basically explains that companies that use unique resources will be able to gain competitive advantage. Product innovation is an intangible and unique resource that can boost financial performance so as to gain a competitive advantage. Process innovation is a more important factor affecting company performance than product innovation and marketing, particularly in organizational structures and manufacturing processes. Process innovation helps organizations to improve productivity and organizational quality, where the quality of output increases, customers will be satisfied and will use them again thereby increasing productivity. Marketing innovation is an intangible and unique resource that can encourage increased financial performance so as to gain a competitive advantage. A company that is always innovating which includes Marketing Innovation, Product Innovation and Process Innovation requires sufficient funding to improve its financial performance. Limited own capital owned by the company, the use of debt is an alternative.

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